

HIGHLY ORTHOTROPIC PANELS STRUCTURAL STABILITY, FARRAR AND BLOCH WAVES THEORY

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This paper presents the studies to develop structural highly orthotropic panels. These types of panels provide the capabilities required for structural morphing. They are highly deformable in one given direction and in the perpendicular one must be compliant to sustain the internal loads per certification stiffness and strength requirements. Neither classic orthotropic panels nor regular cellular solids Bloch wave theories are strictly applicable on their study. A combination of computational method, Matlab coded, to analyze stability and classic structural beam theory is studied. Then, non linear FEM models are developed for an aerospace control surface application; their results are compared with reported Bloch wave sequences on periodic cellular solid panels. The stability along stiffer direction is a requirement to obtain a continuous deformation and plasticization sequence of the cell rows in the perpendicular direction. A sample panel is sized and 3D modelled, and then produced using additive layer manufacturing process to demonstrate the initial stages of a validation and verification campaign.

Keywords: morphing; structures; buckling; highly orthotropic panels; Farrar theory; Bloch waves; additive manufacturing.

1. Introduction

The structural morphing is an active research field to develop more efficient solutions. Open literature contains good examples of the potential application of morphing structures into wind turbine blade applications,¹. In the case of aircraft structures, there are published studies for application into wing high-lift devices,² and wing tips,³. In particular, previous studies sustain the application of this type of morphing solutions into a novel rudder that morphs during deployment,^{4,5}. This novel rudder is the subject of the work presented in this paper. Recently, the EU FP7 Clean Sky program has made public some of the research works on structural morphing. The design of high lift devices than can curve during their deployment is feasible with current state of the art structures and commercially available actuators,⁶. The panel skins of such a device present different

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technical challenges for their development. The partners in EU FP7 SARISTU “Smart Intelligent Aircraft Structures”, have made public, ILA Berlin 2014, a solution based on a bi-material type- it is to say the result of combining rigid aluminium stiffeners with elastomeric members- of panel that can be curved while maintain the adequate mechanical properties.

The studies presented in this paper are the result of the research on defining a different type of structural panel. These panels are based on repeating cells highly orthotropic, which flexibility chord wise is tuned with the one required for the device kinematics deployment. At the same time the span wise direction presents adequate stiffness and strength to sustain aerodynamic loads. These panels are a particular case of the more generic family of cellular solids, ⁷. Figure 1 depicts the different Poisson macro behaviour of the panel depending on the configuration of the cells. This behaviour ranges from standard effect panel to Zero-Poisson with the possibility to develop Auxetic responses.

Fig. 1: Different panel's behaviour depending on cell configuration.

The regular cellular solids, constituted by infinite periodic cells, are traditionally studied for stability under 2D compression forces, ⁸. The particularization to different type of cells can be found in different publications. The cases of isotropic circular and hexagonal lattice are considered in numerous references and being analyzed under different type of loading, ⁹. In the general case, it has been precluded after testing, ¹⁰, that under uni-axial compression loading, these type of cellular panels follow always the same sequence of events, ⁷. Figure 2, depicts¹⁰ this reported panel stress- strain response for two different cellular panels: initial nearly linear response (point 1), then deformation concentrates in a single cell row that starts to plasticize as a local mode that involves (point 2), this cell row is perpendicular to the compression force direction. This row shear collapses with an un-symmetrical failure mode and stays deformed. Then the next row starts with the same failure mode mechanism that keeps on spreading from row to row, following the sequence point 4 to 7. It is relevant that for two types of cell materials with different stress- strain curves and mechanical properties, Young modulus, yield and rupture stress,

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the behaviour is very similar. This cellular panel macro behaviour is positive to store deformation energy, as in aircraft tail bumpers. The use in other aircraft airworthy structures, that require no yield up to limit load and then no rupture to ultimate load, requires no permanent deformation in the first row due to mainly shear induced instability, as it will be summarized later this article.

Fig. 2: Cellular panels, circular left- hexagonal right, stress strain curves, compression uniaxial loading. ^[10]

On the other hand, the buckling behaviour of orthotropic plates is also well reported and the literature presents numerous publications, ¹¹⁻¹³, but there are no previous studies on highly orthotropic plates. The present work summarizes a new set of studies that combine classical beam theory in mechanical engineering, with compression buckling stability based on Farrar methods, ¹⁴. The initial results are the basis to simulate high orthotropic panels' behaviour under loading with non linear FEM models. This new methodology intends to fill the gap to analyze highly orthotropic panels based on repeating basic unitary cell n times, as depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Zero Poisson panel and basic Cell geometry parameters.

The set of parameters, pitch, distances, thickness, etc. are defined to provide panel stability. The stability must be achieved for buckling under compression loading as an initial requirement. This study, in the present case, is based on Matlab coded Farrar theory. Fulfilling this requirement is of capital importance to design the morphing direction to accommodate the induced deformations without reaching failure stresses. The close relation between the load compression behaviour of a panel and its geometric structure, has been studied for flexible foams, ¹⁵. For the highly orthotropic panels, the

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geometry definition of the cells is studied to cope with an initial set of stiffness requirements. The selection of adequate geometrical values to achieve the required strength- stiffness and avoid permanent deformation is studied with classic continuous beam theory. An application for a commercial transport aircraft control surface is cinematically modelled in CATIA 5 to obtain internal loads and stiffness required. ABAQUS highly non linear FEM models are developed to study panel behaviour. ABAQUS is an implicit finite element solver reported to provide accurate results for this type of studies, ¹⁶⁻¹⁸. A representative panel specimen has been manufactured with a novel 3D printing system, commercially available, to initiate validation and verification phases tests based.

2. Methodology

The material considered for the panels is selected based on commercial availability for final additive layer manufacturing or 3D printing. The raw material considered to design and manufacture the panels of this study is Visijet M3 X. This material can be easily processed in a 3-D printing standard device.

Table 1 Visijet M3 X 3D printable material properties. ¹⁹

<i>Properties</i>	<i>Condition</i>	<i>VisiJet M3X</i>
Density @ 80°C (liquid)	ASTM D4164	1.04 g/cm ³
Tensile Strength	ASTM D638	49 MPa
Tensile Modulus	ASTM D638	1340 MPa
Elongation @ break	ASTM D638	3.3%
Yield strength	ASTM D638	20 MPa
Poisson Coefficient	ASTM D638	0.3

The highly orthotropic panels can present different configurations, depending on the cellular selected to be repeated. All the cases under study present common features: springs like type members in the deformable direction, and stiffeners into the perpendicular one, as it is depicted in figure 4.

Fig. 4 Highly orthotropic panel's configurations studied

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In all the studied cases the stiffness properties are obtained; in-plane orthotropic $E_1, E_2, G_{12}, \nu_{12}, \nu_{21}$; out of plane $E_3, G_{13}, G_{23}, \nu_{13}, \nu_{31}, \nu_{23}, \nu_{32}$. The configuration named “V-Plane” has been already characterized,²⁰. This study incorporates the novel “Double-C” configuration that while keeping the basic common geometric features as the V-Plane, shows performance improvements in relation to “V-Plane” one.

Let’s consider an equivalent constant thickness “ t ” orthotropic panel with the same dimensions, width and length as the panel under our study. The equivalent panel incorporates the stiffeners as well. The original highly orthotropic panel stiffeners must provide adequate support to the springs in the perpendicular direction. This is a condition for any kind of loading and panel deformation state. Therefore, in order to assure panel stability, the stiffeners thickness “ t_s ”, height “ d ” and pitch between them “ b ” have to be able to provide stability to the overall panel. The requirement for stiffener stability is a key finding in this study. The critical failure mode for these panels is buckling under compression loading. The applied load flows are set to cope with an application objective. The Farrar theory¹⁴ has been selected to provide compression buckling allowable stresses. It has been programmed in Matlab. This code takes as input the internal compression loads and the geometry constraints, and performs calculations that yield an optimum set of geometrical parameters for the structure. Farrar’s theory states that the optimum structure is one in which the compression stresses at the beginning of the initial buckling σ_B match the corresponding Euler buckling as a column σ_E . In this way when the local buckling is induced, then global buckling of the entire panel starts.

The Farrar theory also defines a reference stress σ_{ref} , and a mean stress σ_m , because the reinforced skin stress distribution is not uniform. The Farrar factor, F , is defined as the ratio between the mean and the reference stress, concluding that the higher the value of F , the more optimum the structure results in terms of weight. “ N ” is the applied compression flow in the panel. Then it is imposed the condition of simultaneous local and global buckling, and both equal to average stress: $\sigma_m = \sigma_B = \sigma_E$. Then F is obtained as a solely function on the geometry parameters, specifically the parameters t_s (stringers thickness), t (equivalent skin thickness), b (distance between stiffeners), d (stiffeners height). The difficulty of application of this theory to a real case is the combination between equations and graphs. In this study, the graphs, for each Farrar factor F level, have been Matlab modelled (Figure 6). So, starting with known values of $R_b = d/b$ and $R_t = t/t_s$, and the graph $F = f(R_b, R_t)$ the values of all the other geometric parameters as functions of the panel length L_{eq} are the following:

$$\sigma_B = \frac{\sigma_B}{\sigma_0} f_1 \left(\frac{A_s}{bt}, \frac{t_s}{t} \right) 3.6E \left(\frac{t}{b} \right)^2 \quad (2.1)$$

$$\sigma_E = \frac{\pi^2 E}{2L_{eq}} \left[\frac{\rho}{b} f_2 \left(\frac{A_s}{bt}, \frac{t_s}{t} \right) \right]^2 b^2 \quad (2.2)$$

- A_s transversal stringers area, height “ d ” and thickness “ t_s ”.

$$A_s = d \cdot t_s \quad (2.3)$$

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- L_{eq} , length of the skins and stringers, for the present case application purpose, pitch between ribs. It is assumed that ribs provide a stable support.
- E equivalent modulus along panel stiffer direction
- σ_0 compression skin buckling as a plate,

$$\sigma_0 = 3.6E \left(\frac{t}{b}\right)^2 \quad (2.4)$$

$$t = \frac{1}{F(1 + R_b R_t)} \left(\frac{N \cdot L_{eq}}{E}\right)^{1/2} \quad (2.5)$$

$$b = 1.103 \frac{\sqrt{F}(1 + R_b R_t)}{[R_b^3 R_t (4 + R_b R_t)]^{1/2}} \left(\frac{N \cdot L_{eq}}{E}\right)^{1/2} \quad (2.6)$$

$$F^4 = \frac{\sigma_B}{\sigma_0} \left(\frac{A_s}{bt}, \frac{t_s}{t}\right) 3.6\pi^2 \left(\left[\frac{\rho}{b} \left(\frac{A_s}{bt}, \frac{t_s}{t}\right)\right]\right)^2 \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{A_s}{bt}\right)} \quad (2.7)$$

The figures 5 to 12 depict the Farrar Plots, obtained with Matlab, for the different geometry parameters: t , d , b and t_s , and for two different panel lengths.

Fig. 5 Matlab Farrar Plots, t values for $L=200$ mm

Fig. 6 Matlab Farrar Plots, t values for $L=100$ mm

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Fig. 7 Matlab Farrar Plots, d for $L=200$ mm

Fig. 8 Matlab Farrar Plots, d for $L=100$ mm

Fig. 9 Matlab Farrar Plots, b for $L=200$ mm

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Fig. 10 Matlab Farrar Plots, b for $L=100$ mm

Fig. 11 Matlab Farrar Plots, t_s for $L=200$ mm

Fig. 12 Matlab Farrar Plots, t_s for $L=100$ mm

3. Unit Cell Analysis

Once the stability of the longitudinal stiffeners is assured, the selection of the cell is critical to define properly the spring like members of the highly orthotropic panel configuration. The previous stability study has provided an equivalent stiffened orthotropic panel that fits the strength requirement in one direction. The continuous beam analysis provides the geometry required on the deformable direction to reach the design goals in terms of adequate stiffness for large deformations.

Let E_0 be the modulus of elasticity of the basic material selected for the panel. The derivation of the panel elasticity modulus in the three main directions of the singular cell can be expressed as function of E_0 . These panel elasticity modules are the result of making an analogy of the actual panel under study with a solid one, constant thickness, and anisotropy behaviour in the three main directions. It is conveyed that the flexible direction elastic modulus is E_1 , in the perpendicular within the plane of the panel, E_2 , and E_3 stiffness panel perpendicular direction.

The selection of these Young modulus target values depends on the application of the panel. The panel must follow the extension kinematics of morphing chord-wise and the stiffness and strength required span-wise. This requirement is translated into a target value of two orders of magnitude difference between E_1 and the pair E_2, E_3 . Then, it is selected a general target value of 10% E_0 for these two last modules.

$$E_2 \cong 0,1E_0; E_3 \cong 0,1E_0$$

Supposing an applied force, P , in direction 2, the deformation of the panel in the direction of this applied force can be expressed as a function of the width of the panel, b , the equivalent thickness t_{eq} and the equivalent elastic modulus E_2 . But also the deformation can be expressed in terms of the thickness, t , height, and d .

$$\varepsilon_2 = \frac{P}{ct_{eq}E_2} \quad (4.1)$$

$$\varepsilon_2 = \frac{P}{tdE_0} \quad (4.2)$$

If the problem is simplified, assuming that the equivalent thickness is the same as the basic stiffener, and by extension all the cell thicknesses are constant, it can be concluded that:

$$E_2 = \frac{d}{c}E_0 \quad (4.3)$$

Imposing the target Young modulus condition, then:

$$d \cong 0,1c \quad (4.4)$$

Similar reasoning for the derivation of E_3 in relation to E_0 can be followed. In this case, the other in-plane panel dimension is named c .

$$\varepsilon_3 = \frac{P}{bcE_3} \quad (4.5)$$

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$$\varepsilon_3 = \frac{P}{t(b+c)E_0} \quad (4.6)$$

$$E_3 = \frac{t(b+c)}{bc} E_0 \quad (4.7)$$

Then, another geometrical constraint for the panel definition is concluded

$$b \cong 20t \quad (4.8)$$

The expression of the latest equivalent elastic modulus, along the most flexible main direction, is going to require using continuous beam theory, symmetries and simplifications, in particular that Euler- Bernoulli theory is valid, and deformations are low enough to assume that perpendicular sections to the deformation line stay perpendicular after loading. It is assumed a constant cell thickness at least one order of magnitude lower than the cell typical dimension. The first basic cell considered is composed by straight beams. The study is then focus on analyzing the segment AB, Figure 13.

Fig. 13: Basic cell sketch and internal loading.

The point B displacements and rotation can be expressed as a function of point A ones:

$$u_B = u_A + \theta_A(y_B - y_A) - \int_A^B \frac{M_f(s)}{E_0 I_z} (y_B - y) ds \quad (4.9)$$

$$v_B = v_A + \theta_A(x_B - x_A) + \int_A^B \frac{M_f(s)}{E_0 I_z} (x_B - x) ds \quad (4.10)$$

$$\theta_B = \theta_A + \int_A^B \frac{M_f(s)}{E_0 I_z} ds \quad (4.11)$$

The point A is in the symmetry plane and horizontal displacement and rotation are zero.

$$u_B = \frac{1}{E_0 I_z} \int_0^l (M_A + P s \cos \theta_0)(s - l) \sin \theta_0 ds \quad (4.12)$$

$$\theta_B = \frac{-1}{E_0 I_z} \int_0^l (M_A + P s \cos \theta_0) ds \quad (4.13)$$

B point displacement in y direction is restricted:

$$0 = v_A + \frac{1}{E_0 I_z} \int_0^l (M_A + P s \cos \theta_0)(l - s) \cos \theta_0 ds \quad (4.14)$$

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Let be P , the applied force along spring extension. The problem is reduced to obtain the value of the four unknown internal loads at A and B points, M_A , H_A , M_B and V_B . There are three equilibrium equations; therefore, the hyper-statics degree of the problem is one.

$$H_A = -P \quad (4.15)$$

$$V_B = 0 \quad (4.16)$$

$$M_B = -M_A - P l \sin \theta_0 \quad (4.17)$$

The energy equation provides a new equation to solve the hyper statics problem. The deformation energy is expressed as a function of the bending moment in the extreme A, M_A , and then minimum energy state is imposed to obtain its value.

$$E = P \cdot u_B + M_B \cdot \theta_B \quad (4.18)$$

$$\frac{dE}{dM_A} = 0 \rightarrow -\sin \theta_0 \frac{l^2}{2} + 2M_A \frac{l}{P} + l^2 \sin \theta_0 + \cos \theta_0 \frac{l^2}{2} = 0 \quad (4.19)$$

$$M_A = \frac{-Pl}{4} (\sin \theta_0 + \cos \theta_0); M_B = \frac{Pl}{4} (\cos \theta_0 - 3 \sin \theta_0) \quad (4.20)$$

The deformation at extreme B, and springs stiffness can be expressed as:

$$\varepsilon_B = \frac{Pl^2}{24E_0I_z} \sin \theta_0 \{3 \tan \theta_0 - 1\} \quad (4.21)$$

$$k = \frac{P}{u_B} = \frac{24E_0I_z}{l^3 \sin \theta_0 \{3 \sin \theta_0 - \cos \theta_0\}} \quad (4.22)$$

This expression can then be incorporated into minimum panel weight to sustain a critical load P_{cr} .

$$W = W(b, c, d, t, \theta_0) = \rho \left(\frac{W}{b} + 1 \right) \frac{12c}{kE_0t^2} \left(\frac{2P_{cr}}{\pi} \right)^2 \quad (4.23)$$

The equivalent Elastic Modulus in “1” direction, can be expressed as

$$E_1 = E_0 \frac{2td^2}{bl^2} \frac{1}{\sin \theta_0 \{3 \tan \theta_0 - 1\}} \quad (4.24)$$

For the purpose of establishing an order of magnitude, and θ_0 geometries between 15° and 80° , then: $t \cong d \cong 0,1l \cong 0,1b \rightarrow E_1 \cong 10^{-3}E_0$. The panel can be designed to present a relative stiffness in one direction, two orders of magnitude lower than in the other two main directions.

A second cell geometry, based on a circular central segment, Figure 14, has been also considered for geometrical definition.

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Fig. 14: Curved cell study.

This hyper-static structure is solved particularizing the more general Rayleigh-Ritz method,²¹. The curved beam segment bending moment is expressed as a function of the hyper-static unknown M_B and then imposing zero rotation at point A.

$$\frac{E_1}{E_0} = \frac{1}{3} \frac{t^3}{cR^2} \frac{\text{sen } \theta_0}{(2\theta_0 + \text{sen } 2\theta_0 - \text{sen}^2\theta_0/\theta_0)} \quad (4.25)$$

As: $t \cong 0,1c \cong 0,1R$ then $E_1 \cong 10^{-3}E_0$. The same elastic modulus relation is achieved.

The last configuration is a mixed one, straight and curved segment, Figure 15.

Fig. 15: Mixed cell study.

Following the same approach,

$$\frac{E_1}{E_0} = \frac{t^3(R\theta_0 + l)(l \cos \theta_0 + R \sin \theta_0)}{c(a_1 R^3 l + a_2 R^2 l^2 + a_3 R l^3 + a_4 l^4 + a_5 R^4)} \quad (4.26)$$

The constants in this expression are:

$$a_1 = 30 \cos \theta_0 + 6\theta_0 - 12\theta_0 \cos^2 \theta_0 \quad (4.27)$$

$$a_2 = 12(1 + \theta_0 \sin \theta_0 \cos \theta_0 - \cos^2 \theta_0) \quad (4.28)$$

$$a_3 = 3(\theta_0^3 - \theta_0 \cos \theta_0) \quad (4.29)$$

$$a_4 = \cos^2 \theta_0 \quad (4.30)$$

$$a_5 = (\theta_0 \sin \theta_0 \cos \theta_0 + \theta_0^2 - 12 \cos^2 \theta_0) \quad (4.31)$$

As: $t \cong 0,1c \cong 0,1R$ then $E_1 \cong 10^{-3}E_0$ as in the previous cells cases.

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4. Structural application, design, FEM models and manufacturing

The structural feasibility of this design is verified integrating the morphing skin structure in solid CATIA 5 models for kinematic mechanical analysis and simulation on a novel rudder structure for a commercial transport aircraft, ⁵. Figure 16 depicts some of the geometrical details of these 3D models.

Fig. 16 Morphing Rudder applications of the highly orthotropic panels

The stiffness and loading for this application have been obtained with kinematics analysis based on CATIA 5 models, Figure 17.

Fig. 17 Control surface kinematics studies, displacements at 30° deflection

This structure is FEM modelled with ABAQUS, to obtain the internal stresses distribution, Figure 18, just for deflection induced external loading. The plasticized zone is concentrated in the longitudinal stiffeners mainly (read areas). This stress concentration couples with the longitudinal internal forces when the structure is also loaded with the aerodynamic and inertial loads. This explains the importance of stability on the stiffeners. The stress concentrations on the stiffeners are mainly shear induced and when combined with compression stresses, overall panel un-stability appears due to stiffener out of plane displacement, collapsing the structure.

Fig. 18 Von Misses stresses at highly deformable panels at 30° deflection

The maximum Von Mises stresses and the logarithmic strains in the highly deformable panels have been extracted from different ABAQUS executions for the control surface deflected between 5 and 30 degrees. The table 2 includes the values.

Table 2 Maximum Von Mises stresses and logarithmic strains in the highly deformable panels for the control surface deflected between 5 and 30 degrees.

Deflection	5°	10°	15°	20°	25°	30°
Upper Panel						
$\sigma_{VM_{max}}$	10.3	19.8	19.9	20.9	22.2	23.5
$LE(10^{-3})$	8.1	16.5	26.5	36.5	46.1	55.0
Lower Panel						
$\sigma_{VM_{max}}$	10.5	19.8	19.9	20.5	21.9	23.3
$LE(10^{-3})$	7.9	16.4	28.1	38.6	48.7	59.0

Fig. 19 Maximum Von Mises stresses at highly deformable panels

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There is an initial linear answer of panel stresses with lower deflections, up to 10° , Figure 19. Then a plastic behaviour between 10 and 15° is obtained, before a second linear answer between 15 and 30° appears. It is noticed that the material plasticity appears between 10° and 12° deflection. It results in an analogy between this FEM model predictions on the resultant panels stress- strain curves in relation to the reported for cellular solid panels Bloch wave sequences, but with some remarkable differences. There is an initial linear response, then first material plasticization appears in one row of the panel and new elastic response with a more relaxed secondary Young modulus appears. Therefore a design principle based in reinforcing the initial row that plasticizes, to increase the principal Young modulus answer and delay the appearance of the secondary elastic zone can be concluded as adequate. There is a need to ensure that no rupture stress is reached in the plasticized area.

An optimization in terms of thickness and height for the rest of cells rows is a continuation of these studies for design for minimum material weight performance in the future. The generation of a similar Bloch wave plasticization sequence, like on repeated circular and hexagonal cells solids panels, can provide a minimum material and weight panel configuration, while fulfilling the requirements.

The 3D printing “Double-C” representative panel in the selected material VisiJet M 3X has been performed, dimensions $230 \times 230 \times 30$ mm and typical wall thickness 2 mm, Figure 20.

Fig. 20 3D printed panel specimen

The 3D printer has been a ProJet ® 7000 MP based on stereo-lithography technology. The amount of material used was 210 grams. The time consumed has been around 7 hours. The time to produce the panel is proportional to the amount of material used. Even if 3D printing technologies in the future enable a better cycle performance, and the

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weight is not critical for a particular application, the need to minimize the amount of material will keep on being of importance, from serial manufacturing process productivity point of view.

Currently panel specimens are ready for a campaign testing to complete validation. The verification campaign will allow the comparison of the empirical results with the analytical ones.

5. Conclusions

This approach is valid to design a highly orthotropic panel, based on the repetition of a modular geometrical cell, to cope with two order of magnitude stiffness ratio requirements, in the two in-plane main directions, and the strength requirements. Setting stiffeners configuration for stability is required to design the panel and then the unit cells. This method serves for sizing and producing highly deformable panels that configure part of a morphing rudder structure for a commercial transport aircraft that is compliant with strength and stiffness requirements. Numerical analysis based on non linear FEM models, predicts a similar Bloch wave behaviour that on regular cellular solids, constituted by infinite periodic cells. The panels develop secondary elasticity response. Further studies are required to optimize deformable direction cells geometry, from weight and 3D manufacturing process productivity stand points. Testing campaign is required to initiate validation and verification stages. These tests include static and fatigue loading, and also environmental effects on mechanical properties degradation. Further studies are required to obtain new materials more suitable for the mechanical requirements and optimized panel configurations.

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